

THIAZOLE DERIVATIVES AS ANTISPASMODICS AND ANTIHISTAMINICS. PART III

BY PRANABANDHU TRIPATHY, H. K. PUJARI AND M. K. ROUf

Four different series of compounds, prepared by reacting 4-aryl-2-aminothiazoles with paraformaldehyde and one of the following: (a) a ketone (several ketones have been used), (b) 1-phenyl-3-methyl-5-pyrazolone, (c) 8-hydroxyquinoline and (d) diethylamine, have been studied for spasmolytic and antihistaminic action. The one formed with 2-aminotetrahydrobenzothiazole, paraformaldehyde and 1-phenyl-3-methyl-5-pyrazolone has proved most effective.

Of these, 4-aryl-2-(1-phenyl-3-methyl-5-keto-4-pyrazolinyl)-methylenethiazoles have been found to possess significant antispasmodic and antihistaminic activities.

In view of the antispasmodic activity of certain substituted β -aminoalkylaryl ketones (Blicke, *Ann. Rev. Biochem.*, 1943, 13, 549; Denton *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 71, 2048), pyrazolone derivatives (Notkin and Webster, *Rev. Canadian Biol.*, 1942, 1, 660; Pathak and Ghosh, this *Journal*, 1949, 26, 371) and pyridyl- and thiazolyl-quinoline derivatives (Heilbron *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 419), it was thought of interest to prepare in the present investigation some *p*-aminoketones with thiazolyl substituents attached to the secondary amino groups and also to synthesise thiazolyl-quinoline and thiazolyl- or benzothiazolyl-pyrazolone derivatives for use as antispasmodics. Thiazoles have been taken up for investigation as some thiazole derivatives described by Chance, Dirnhuber and Robinson are found to exhibit musculotropic activity (*Brit. J. Pharmacol.*, 1946, 1, 153) and the presence of sulphur-containing groups like thiazolyl, thienyl etc. may promote antispasmodic activity, as indicated by the observation of Blicke and Taso (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 66, 1645) and of Anderson and Green (*Nature*, 1950, 165, 122).

Because of the observation of Erlenmeyer and Müller (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1945, 28, 922), Sondern and Breivogel (U.S. Patent 2,440,730/1948), Dahlbon (*Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1950, 4, 744) and Kaye and Parris (*J. Org. Chem.*, 1951, 16, 1761); it was also proposed to test the above compounds as antihistaminics. Virtually all the antihistaminic compounds contain the structural unit $R_2N-C-C-X$ in which X is a group beginning with oxygen ($R_2N-C-C-O-$), nitrogen ($R_2N-C-C-N<$) or carbon ($R_2N-C-C-C-$). Therefore attempts were made to introduce the latter

group into thiazole nucleus by condensing it with paraformaldehyde and ketones or ketomethylene compounds with the hope of synthesising possible efficient antihistaminics.

Condensation of thiazole compounds with quinoline or pyrazolone would also help to study how the attachment of an additional therapeutically active quinoline or pyrazolone nucleus adds to the importance of thiazoles in therapy, particularly as antispasmodics and antihistaminics.

In the present investigation 4-phenyl-, 4-*p*-hydroxy-*m*-methoxyphenyl-, 4-phenylethyl-, and 4- β -naphthyl-2-aminothiazoles have been prepared by the method of Dodson and King (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 2243). These thiazoles have been condensed with different ketones and formaldehyde.

Similarly, three other series of thiazole derivatives have also been prepared by substituting one of the following: (a) 1-phenyl-3-methyl-5-pyrazolone, (b) 8-hydroxy-quiuoline and (c) diethylamine, for ketones in the synthesis of the first series.

All these four series of thiazole derivatives have been screened for their antispasmodic and antihistaminic action in the S.C.B. Medical College, Cuttack, Orissa, under the supervision of Dr. J. K. Mohanty.

Of all the compounds reported in this paper, compounds III, VII, XVII have been found to possess pronounced antihistaminic as well as antispasmodic activity. Particularly compound III has been found to exhibit third of the activity of antazoline hydrochloride.

Compounds VIII and X also possess antispasmodic action in concentrations varying from 2×10^{-5} to 2×10^{-6} . Detailed procedure and results of these will be published elsewhere.

EXPERIMENTAL

Condensation of 4-Phenyl-2-aminothiazole with Formaldehyde and Acetophenone (I).—A mixture of 4-phenyl-2-aminothiazole (1.76 g.), acetophenone (1.2 g.) and paraformaldehyde (0.9 g.) in HCl (conc., 3 c.c.) and alcohol (25 c.c.) was heated under reflux for 2 hours. An additional amount of paraformaldehyde (0.6 g.) was then added and refluxing continued for 3 hours more. The alcohol was distilled off when a pasty mass was obtained which on keeping in contact with ammonia for 2 to 3 hours solidified. It was washed well with water and recrystallised from alcohol, m.p. 115°, yield 82%. (Found: N, 9.0; S, 9.98. $C_{18}H_{15}ON_2S$ requires N, 9.09; S, 10.39%).

The properties and analytical data of the other condensation products are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Comp. No.	R =	R' =	Yield.	M.P.	% Nitrogen.		% Sulphur.	
					Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
VI	C_6H_5-	$-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OH}(p)$	88%	78°	8.20	8.28	9.25	9.47
VII	C_6H_5-	$-\text{CH}_2\text{COC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OH}(p)$	72	89°	8.40	8.64	9.62	9.88
VIII	C_6H_5-	$-\text{CH}_2\text{COCH}=\text{CHC}_6\text{H}_5$	75	130°	8.20	8.38	9.40	9.58
IX	C_6H_5-	$-\text{CH}_2\text{CO}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{OH}(p)$	85	81°	7.92	8.09	9.64	9.25
X	C_6H_5-	$-\text{CH}_2\text{COC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OCH}_3(p)$	75	86°	8.10	8.28	9.10	9.47
XI	$C_6H_5\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2-$	$-\text{CH}_2\text{COC}_6\text{H}_5$	80	145°	8.50	8.34	9.60	9.52
XII	$(p)\text{HOC}_6\text{H}_4-$	$-\text{CH}_2\text{COC}_6\text{H}_5$	70	180°(d)	8.85	8.64	9.95	9.88
XIII	$(p)\text{HOC}_6\text{H}_3-$	$-\text{CH}_2\text{COC}_6\text{H}_5$	75	160°(d)	8.12	8.09	9.80	9.25
XIV	$\beta\text{-C}_{10}\text{H}_7$	$-\text{CH}_2\text{COC}_6\text{H}_5$	70	132°	7.70	7.82	8.70	8.94

4-Phenyl-2-(1'-phenyl-3-methyl-5'-keto-4'-pyrazolonyl)-methylaminothiazole (II).—A mixture consisting of 1-phenyl-3-methyl-5-pyrazolone (1.73 g.) (prepared by the method described in "Quantitative Organic Analysis" By Vogel), paraformaldehyde (1.2 g.) and 4-phenyl-2-aminothiazole (1.76 g.) in HCl (conc., 3 c.c.) and alcohol (25 c.c.) was refluxed over an asbestos-wire gauge for 8 hours. After reflux the alcohol was distilled off and the mass was poured into a large volume of water. The gummy product, thus obtained, hardened up in contact with ammonia (conc.). It was purified by dissolving in NaOH and reprecipitating with acetic acid, m.p. 121°, yield 85%. (Found: N, 15.3; S, 8.9. $C_{20}H_{18}ON_4S$ requires N, 15.47; S, 8.84%.)

Condensation of 2-Amino-4:5:6:7-tetrahydrobenzothiazole with 1-Phenyl-3-methylpyrazolone (III).—A mixture of 1-phenyl-3-methylpyrazolone (1.73 g.), 2-amino-4:5:6:7-tetrahydrobenzothiazole (2.3 g.) and paraformaldehyde (1.2 g.) in HCl (conc., 3 c.c.) and alcohol (20 c.c.) was refluxed for 8 hours. The compound was separated and purified as above, m.p. 102° (decomp.), yield 82%. (Found: N, 16.3; S, 9.6. $C_{18}H_{21}ON_4S$ requires N, 16.4; S, 9.4%.)

The properties and analytical data of the different condensation products are described in Table II.

TABLE II

Comp. No.	R=	Yield.	M.P.	% Nitrogen.		% Sulphur.	
				Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
XV	(p) HO (m) H ₃ CO } C ₆ H ₃	78%	180°(d)	13.60	13.73	7.80	7.84
XVI	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂ CH ₂	80	145-46°	14.30	14.32	9.10	8.20
XVII	(p) HO.C ₆ H ₄	65	160°(d)	14.44	14.51	8.10	8.47
XVIII	β-C ₁₀ H ₇	85	158°	13.70	13.59	7.90	7.77

4-Phenyl-2-(8'-hydroxy-7'-quinolonyl)-methylaminothiazole (IV).—A mixture of 8-hydroxyquinoline (1.76 g.), 4-phenyl-2-aminothiazole (1.76 g.) and paraformaldehyde (1.2 g.) in HCl (conc., 3 c.c.) and alcohol (25 c.c.) was heated under reflux, and the desired product was isolated in the same manner as described above, m.p. 101°, yield 65%. (Found: N, 12.8; S, 10.0. $C_{18}H_{18}ON_3S$ requires N, 12.61; S, 9.6%.)

2-Acetamido-4-phenyl-5-diethylaminomethylthiazole (V).—2-Acetamido-4-phenylthiazole (2.1 g.) (obtained by acetylating 2-amino 4-phenylthiazole) was taken and to it diethylamine (0.6 g.) in acetic acid (5 c.c.) and formalin (1 c.c.) were added. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 8 hours on a water-bath. After heating, it was diluted with 10 c.c. of water and was then treated with a saturated solution of K₂CO₃ solution. The precipitate, thus obtained, was filtered, washed well with water

and finally recrystallised from alcohol, and dried in a vacuum desiccator, m.p. 80°, yield 75%. (Found: N, 14.02; S, 10.38. $C_{16}H_{21}ON_2S$ requires N, 13.87; S, 10.56%).

The properties and analytical data of the other condensation products are illustrated in Table III.

TABLE III

Comp. No.	R=	Yield.	M.P.	% Nitrogen.		% Sulphur.	
				Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
XIX	$C_6H_5CH_2CH_2-$	80%	188°(d)	12.70	12.69	9.60	9.67
XX	$\beta-C_{10}H_{79}$	85	245°(d)	11.78	11.90	8.70	9.06

The authors are grateful to the Board of Scientific and Industrial Research, Orissa, for research grants to carry out this investigation and to Dr. J. K. Mohanty, Assistant Prof. of Pharmacology, Orissa Medical College, for help in carrying out these tests.

MAYURBHANJ CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
 RAVENSHAW COLLEGE,
 CUTTACK-3.

Received January 10, 1958.